

membrane is manipulated with utmost care and is only handled at the edges with forceps. The following is our procedure for hybridizing probes to DNA transferred on Hybond-N⁺.

Blots are hybridized at 68 °C overnight in plastic boxes or sealed plastic bags using the following hybridization solution: 5X SSC; dried skim milk, 0.5%; sarcosyl, 0.1%; SDS, 0.02%; and salmon sperm DNA, 100 µg/ml. Blots are pre-hybridized initially for at least an hour in the solution without the probe. About 2.5 ml of probe-containing hybridization solution is used per 100-cm² blot. Probes are denatured by boiling for 15 min in a water bath prior to addition to the hybridization solution. After hybridization, the following stringency washes are performed: twice for 5 min at room temperature with 2X SSC, 0.1% SDS; and twice for 15 min at 68 °C with 0.1X SSC, 0.1% SDS. The prehybridization and probe-containing hybridization solution may be kept at -20 °C and reused several times. The probe should be denatured, however, by boiling the solution in a water bath for 15 min before use.

Detection of hybrids

Chromogenic method. The following incubations for detection of probe-hybrids are performed at room temperature. The blot is washed for 1 min with buffer 1 (Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 100 mM; and 150 mM NaCl) and incubated in buffer 2 (buffer 1 with 100 µg/ml sheared salmon sperm DNA and 2% dried skim milk or casein, or 0.5% blocking reagent [Boehringer Mannheim]) for 30 min. Buffer 2 is replaced with buffer 1 containing 150 mU/ml anti-DIG alkaline phosphatase conjugate (anti-DIG-AP [Boehringer Mannheim]) and the blot is incubated for another 30 min. Unbound anti-DIG-AP is then removed by two rinses of buffer 1 (plus 0.3% Tween 20), each for 15 min. The blot is washed for 2 min in buffer 3 (Tris-HCl, pH 9.5, 100 mM; NaCl, 100 mM; and MgCl₂, 50 mM) and incubated with color substrate. The color substrate is prepared by adding 45 µl NBT (nitroblue tetrazolium salt, 75 mg/ml in 70% dimethylformamide) and 35 µl BCIP

(toluidinium salt of 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphate, 50 mg/ml in dimethylformamide) to 10 ml of buffer 3. Hybrid signals are visible after 1-2 h. The intensity of the signals is adjusted by shortening or prolonging the incubation of blots in the color substrate, but this is normally less than a day. After maximum strength of signals is reached, the blots are washed twice in distilled water and dried. Buffer 2 can be reused several times if kept frozen during storage. The anti-DIG-AP solution in buffer 1 may also be reused if several blots have to be processed but it is only active within 12 h at 4 °C. Color blots can be reprobated, although somewhat laboriously, by washing off the stain with dimethylformamide at 65 °C. After decolorization, the probe is stripped off by incubating the blots twice in 0.4 M NaOH for 15 min at 45 °C. Blots are then rinsed with water and washed twice for 5 min with 2X SSC

at room temperature. The blots may be stored dry or used directly for reprobating.

Luminescent method. This is the method of choice for blots that require frequent reprobating and is based on the emission of light during the dephosphorylation of AMPPD (3-[2'-spiroadamantane]-4-methoxy-4-[3'-phosphoryloxy]-phenyl-1,2-dioxetane). This procedure is similar to the chromogenic technique except that the substrate solution contains AMPPD instead (100 µg/ml AMPPD in buffer 3). Blots in AMPPD solutions are wrapped neatly in clingfilm. X-ray film is exposed to these blots for 15 min or more (depending on the intensity of signals). Multiple exposures are possible since the light emission persists for 24 h. The AMPPD solution in buffer 3 can be reused up to five times within 2 mo of preparation. Probes are stripped in a manner similar to that in the chromogenic method. ■

Nonradioactive DNA analysis using biotin labeling and chemiluminescent detection

C. M. Vera Cruz, Plant Pathology Department, Kansas State University (KSU), Manhattan, Kansas; A. K. Raymundo, Institute of Biological Sciences, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, Philippines; and J. E. Leach, KSU, Kansas, USA

The most common method for detecting DNA in blots involves using radioactively labeled probes. Technical advances in nonradioactive detection methodologies have made these attractive alternatives. The reagents for nonradioactive DNA analysis are relatively stable (the half-life of the most commonly used radioisotope, ³²P, is 14 d). Using nonradioactive labeling reduces the frequency of shipping perishable and hazardous materials. Using nonradioactive probes eliminates exposure to radioactive materials and disposal of radioactive waste. Additionally, labeled probes are stable for at least several months.

Several types of labeling and detection kits are available commercially. They vary in molecules used for labeling DNA (the ligand) and the labeling and detec-

tion methods. The biotin-avidin system is one of the most widely used nonradioactive labeling methods. Biotin is incorporated into the probe DNA as biotin-11-dUTP. Subsequently, avidin conjugated to alkaline phosphatase is bound to the biotin. The complex is detected using a chemiluminescent substrate for alkaline phosphatase (AMPPD, 3-[2'-spiroadamantane]-4-methoxy-4-[3'-phosphoryloxy]-phenyl-1,2-dioxetane). A simplified protocol based on the biotin-avidin system follows.

DNA labeling and detection

Biotin, purchased as biotin-11-dUTP, is substituted for dTTP in labeling reactions. The biotin can be incorporated into the DNA probe by nick translation, random priming, or amplification using polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Commercially prepared kits are available for each of these methods. The protocols for labeling and detection described here have been used with kits from Tropix (47 Wiggins Ave., Bedford, Massachusetts 01730, USA).

DNA labeling using nick translation. Add the following to a microcentrifuge tube: 10 µl of DNA sample containing 0.03-2 µg DNA, 3 µl of dNTP mixture,

1 µl of biotin-11-dUTP, 2 µl of buffer concentrate, 2 µl of sterile distilled water, and 2 µl of enzyme mix. Mix by repeated pipetting. Centrifuge for a few seconds. Incubate tube for 30-60 min at 15 °C. Add composition or heat at 65 °C for 10 min to stop reaction. The labeled probe can be used without further purification.

Hybridization and washing

Hybridization. Prehybridize blot in a plastic bag or box with sufficient hybridization solution to cover it (Table 1). Incubate for 6 h at 65 °C without shaking. Denature the labeled probe by boiling for 10 min. If desired, include labeled marker DNA corresponding to size standard on blot. Add denatured probe directly to hybridization solution. Mix and reincubate for 6-14 h at 65 °C with gentle shaking. Store hybridization solution at -20 °C for future use.

Washing of blots. Wash blots twice with wash solution 1 for 5 min each time at 65 °C with gentle shaking and then twice with wash solution 2 for 15 min under the same conditions. (See Table 2 for preparation of wash solutions.)

Signal detection by the AMPPD method

All steps are done with gentle shaking at room temperature. Wash blots briefly in 1X SSC. Wash blots in blocking buffer twice for 5 min and once for at least 20 min. (Blocking buffer is prepared by adding 0.1% Tween 20 [polyoxyethylene sorbitan monolaurate] to 1X conjugate buffer [stir 1% dried skim milk or casein into 1X phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Table 2) and microwave for 45 s or dissolve under low heat and mix].) Blots can be left overnight at this point. Cover the blot with 10 ml of the AVIDx-AP conjugate buffer and incubate for 30 min. (AVIDx-AP conjugate buffer [1:10000] is prepared by spinning AVIDx-AP conjugate for 4 min and then adding 1 µl supernatant to 10 ml conjugate buffer.) Adjust amount so that blot is submerged, about 10 ml/100 cm² blot. Wash blots once in blocking buffer for

Table 1. Hybridization solution.

Solution	Stock	Amount	
		ml/50 ml	ml/100 ml
1 mM EDTA	0.5 M EDTA	0.1	0.2
7% SDS	20% SDS	17.5	35.0
0.25 M disodium phosphate, pH 7.2	0.5 M	25.0	50.0
Boiled salmon sperm DNA, 300 µg/ml ^a	10 mg/ml	1.5	3.0

^a10 mg/ml salmon sperm DNA in distilled water. Autoclave twice, aliquot, and store at -20 °C. (Herring sperm DNA is an alternative to salmon sperm DNA.)

Table 2. Solutions for detection of biotin-labeled DNA.

Solution	Stock		Amount (ml/100 ml)	
	SSC	SDS	SSC	SDS
2X SSC, 1.0% SDS (Solution 1)	20X	20%	10	5
0.1X SSC, 1.0% SDS (Solution 2)	20X	20%	0.5	5
1X SSC	20X		5	
<i>10X phosphate buffered saline^a</i>		<i>1000 ml</i>		
	0.58 M Na ₂ HPO ₄		82.3 g Na ₂ HPO ₄	
	0.17 M NaH ₂ PO ₄		23.5 g NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	
	0.68 M NaCl		40.0 g NaCl	

^aMix Na₂HPO₄ in 500 ml in small amounts at low heat to dissolve completely. Add NaH₂PO₄·H₂O in small amounts until completely dissolved. Add NaCl; dissolve completely (pH 8.2; 1X solution is about pH 7.3-7.4).

10 min. Wash in wash buffer four times for 5 min, and with assay buffer twice for 5 min. (Wash buffer is prepared by adding 0.3% Tween 20 to 1X PBS. Assay buffer is prepared by using 0.1 M diethanolamine [if solid, liquefy at 37 °C], 0.96 ml/100 ml and 1 mM MgCl₂ [stock is 0.5 M], 0.20 ml/100 ml.)

Incubate blots singly in AMPPD solution (50 µg/ml in assay buffer) for 5 min. Store used AMPPD solution at 4 °C; it can be reused at least eight times. Remove excess solution from blot by laying it briefly on a paper towel. Wrap the blots in plastic wrap and arrange in an X-ray cassette. In the dark room, place a film on the blots in the cassette and expose it for a 30-min test exposure. Develop the film. Expose for a longer or shorter period if needed. Luminescence continues for at least 24 h.

Reprobing

Keep blot moist in plastic wrap if it is to be reprobed. Heat 1X SSC with 1% SDS to 95 °C. Pour over the blot and agitate

rapidly for 5 min at room temperature. Repeat twice. Wash blots twice for 5 min with 1X SSC at room temperature and air-dry or store wet in plastic wrap at 4 °C. ■

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